

THE INCLUSION OF SHEAR EFFECTS IN A HERMITIAN FINITE ELEMENT FOR HIGHLY ANISOTROPIC LAMINATED PLATES

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ABSTRACT

A formulation for including the effect of transverse shear deformations in highly anisotropic plates is presented. The interpolation functions are characterized by the tensorial product of Hermitian polynomials corrected for the transverse shear effects. The correction introduces the equilibrium equations uncoupled in x and y allowing to obtain new relations between cross-section rotations and the deflection of the plate. The new interpolation functions are deduced of that, by the application of a linear operator to the Hermitian polynomials and combined in two dimensions to specify a rectangular displacement field corresponding to the tensorial product of these functions. The in-plane displacement field is built with assuring the compatibility of the displacements coupled by the effects of anisotropy and the compatibility at the interface of two non-coplanar elements. So, a new linear operator is applied to the stiffness matrix built without the account of the transverse shear effects. The method does not add extra degrees of freedom to the final element, and eliminates the problem of shear locking which allows the using of thick and thin plate formulations alternatively. Some examples of highly anisotropic plates are treated for the study of the accuracy and convergence of the element by comparison with analytical and numerical solutions.

INTRODUCTION

A very large number of plate elements has been proposed in the literature, whose the formulations for a important part of them are based on the Love-Kirchhoff hypothesis neglecting the shear deformation effects. These elements have been in a first time built for homogeneous isotropic materials and after homogeneous orthotropic materials. Furthermore these elements have been modified to respond to the appearance of new types of materials: heterogeneous, anisotropic and multilayered composites materials, in which the thickness effect on the behaviour plate is more pronounced than in isotropic plates returning inadequate the Kirchhoff-Love kinematic assumption. But not much elements have been conceived directly for these materials.

A Mindlin thick plate theory, taking into account the shear deformation effects, can be developed according two methods of approach. The first consists in to add the degrees of freedom representing shear deformations to the degrees characterized the thin plate formulation. The second method uses independent interpolation functions for displacements and cross-sectional rotations. These two methods present some disadvantages. The first one increases the number of d.o.f. and make the application of boundary conditions difficult, the second presents the tendency for over stiff results to be obtained, when the length to thickness ratio becomes large; this is the shear locking phenomenon. Some possibilities for avoiding locking exist and in particular the use of reduced and selective integration, of the stiffness matrix terms. However, the use of the reduced and selective integration is not always successful, involving zero energy modes Mindlin plate elements and causing mesh instabilities.

A formulation for including the effect of transverse shear deformations in highly anisotropic plates is presented. The interpolation functions are characterized by the tensorial product of Hermitian polynomials corrected for the transverse shear effects. The correction introduces the equilibrium equations uncoupled in x and y allowing to obtain new relations between cross-section rotations and the deflection of the plate. The new interpolation functions are deduced of that, by the application of a linear operator to the Hermitian polynomials and combined in two dimensions to specify a rectangular displacement field corresponding to the tensorial product of these functions. The in-plane displacement field is built with assuring the compatibility of the displacements coupled by the effects of anisotropy and the compatibility at the interface of two non-coplanar elements. So, a new linear operator is applied to the stiffness matrix built without the account of the transverse shear effects. The method does not add extra degrees of freedom to the final element, and eliminates the problem of shear locking which allows the using of thick and thin plate formulations alternatively. Some examples of highly anisotropic plates are treated for the study of the accuracy and convergence of the element by comparison with analytical and numerical solutions. The thin plate formulation before the application of the linear operator has been previously described.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

We consider a plate of thickness h composed of anisotropic layers bonded together. The origin of a Cartesian coordinate system is located within the central plane (x_1-x_2) with the x_3 axis being normal to this plane.

a) Constitutive relations

Here is considered the classical linear theory of laminated anisotropic thick plates in small deflections of Yang, Norris and Stavsky [2] using the Timoshenko assumption for the formulation of shear deformations based upon the following displacement field.

$$\begin{aligned} u_\alpha(x_1, x_2, x_3) &= u_\alpha^0(x_1, x_2) + x_3 \cdot \epsilon_{\gamma 3 \alpha} \theta_\gamma(x_1, x_2) \\ u_3(x_1, x_2, x_3) &= u_3^0(x_1, x_2) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

u_1, u_2, u_3 are the displacements in respective x_1, x_2, x_3 directions; u_1^0, u_2^0, u_3^0 are the corresponding midplane displacements; θ_1, θ_2 are the cross-sectional rotations; and $\epsilon_{\gamma 3 \alpha}$ the permutation tensor.

Substituting (1) into the strain-displacements relations of linear elasticity the equations of deformation are:

$$*\epsilon_{\alpha\beta} = \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^0 + x_3 \cdot \chi_{\alpha\beta} \quad \text{with} \quad \epsilon_{\alpha\beta}^0 = \frac{1}{2} (u_{i,j}^0 + u_{j,i}^0) \quad (2-a)$$

$$\text{and} \quad \chi_{\alpha\beta} = \frac{1}{2} (\epsilon_{\gamma 3 \alpha} \theta_{\gamma,\beta} + \epsilon_{\gamma 3 \beta} \theta_{\gamma,\alpha}) \quad (2-b)$$

$$*\gamma_{3\beta} = (u_{3,\beta} + u_{\beta,3}) = (u_{3,\beta}^0 + \epsilon_{\gamma 3 \beta} \theta_\gamma) \quad (3)$$

Each layer is assumed to possess a plane of elastic symmetry parallel to the central plane. Thus the constitutive relations for any layer are given by the following relation:

$$\sigma_{\alpha\beta} = (C_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} - \frac{C_{\alpha\beta 33} C_{33\gamma\delta}}{C_{3333}}) \cdot \epsilon_{\gamma\delta} \quad \text{with} \quad (\alpha\beta\gamma\delta) \in [1, 2] \quad (4-a)$$

$$\sigma_{3\beta} = 2 \cdot C_{3\beta 3\delta} \cdot \epsilon_{3\delta} \quad (4-b)$$

where C_{ijkl} are the components of the elastic stiffness matrix.

The application of the through-thickness integrations define the generalized plate constitutive equations.

$$\begin{pmatrix} N_{\alpha\beta} \\ M_{\alpha\beta} \\ Q_\alpha \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} & B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} & 0 \\ B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} & D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A^*_{3\alpha 3\delta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon^0_{\gamma\delta} \\ \chi_{\gamma\delta} \\ \gamma_{3\delta} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The $A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}, B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}, D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}, A^*_{3\alpha 3\delta}$ are the respective stretching, bending-stretching, bending, transverse shear stiffnesses defined as follows:

$$(A_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}, B_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}, D_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta}) = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} (1, x_3, x_3^2) \cdot \bar{C}_{\alpha\beta\gamma\delta} dx_3 \quad (6)$$

$$A^*_{3\alpha 3\delta} = k_\alpha \cdot k_\beta \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \bar{C}_{3\alpha 3\delta} dx_3 \quad \text{with} \quad \bar{C}_{3\alpha 3\delta} = C_{3\alpha 3\delta}$$

k_α and k_β the shear correction coefficients.

FINITE-ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Here, is presented a method of developing a stiffness matrix for a rectangular, moderately thick anisotropic plate element. This method use the Hermitian polynomials [1] corrected for the transverse shear effects. This correction introduce the equilibrium equations, uncoupled in x_1 and x_2 , allowing to obtain new relations between $\theta_2(x_1)$ and $u_3(x_1)$, $\theta_1(x_2)$ and $u_3(x_2)$. It is deduced of that ,the new interpolation functions, by the application of an linear operator to the Hermitian polynomials and combined in two dimensions to specify a rectangular displacement field corresponding to a tensorial product of these functions. So, it is displayed a new linear operator applying to the stiffness matrix built without the accounted of the transverse shear effects.

Displacement field :

for the transversal displacement u_3 the displacement field is cubic in x_1 - x_2 with the usual Hermitian interpolation functions and corrected for to take into account the transverse shear effects. The correction introduces the equilibrium equations incoupled in x_1 and x_2

$$\begin{aligned} M_{\alpha\alpha,\alpha} - Q_{\alpha} &= 0 \\ N_{\alpha\alpha,\alpha} &= 0 && + \text{relation 5} \\ Q_{\alpha,\alpha} + q &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

it is deduced of that two independant differential equations whose the particular solutions allow to write the shear transverse deformations in terms of the third derivative in x_1 or x_2 of the deflection

$$\gamma_{3\alpha}(x_{\alpha}) = \frac{-\left(D_{\alpha\alpha\alpha\alpha} - \frac{B_{\alpha\alpha\alpha\alpha}^2}{A_{\alpha\alpha\alpha\alpha}}\right)}{A_{3\alpha3\alpha}^*} u_{3,\alpha\alpha\alpha}^0(x_{\alpha}) = -c_{3\alpha} u_{3,\alpha\alpha\alpha}^0(x_{\alpha}) \quad (8)$$

then the cross-section rotation can be obtained by the following relation

$$\theta_{\alpha} = \varepsilon_{\alpha 3 \gamma} \cdot (u_{3,\gamma}^0 + c_{\gamma 3} u_{3,\gamma\gamma\gamma}^0) \quad (9)$$

the new interpolation functions (fig. 1) are deduced of that by application of a linear operator to the Hermitian polynomials and combined in two dimensions to specify a rectangular displacement field corresponding to the tensorial product of these functions.

figure (1)

for the in-plane displacement, partly cubic, partly linear in order to assure the compatibility of the displacements coupled by the effects of anisotropy and the compatibility at the interface of two non-coplanar elements [10].

Nodal degree-of-freedom nomenclature:

The present element is a eight-noded plate-membrane element called **Hermitian Rectangular Plate-Membrane element with Shear (HRPMS)** which is in fact the extension of the **HRPM** element [9] [10] for the thin highly anisotropic plates. The geometry and nodal degree-of-freedom nomenclature used for this element is shown in figure (2).

figure (2)

Formulation of stiffness matrix:

The HRPM-S stiffness matrix corresponding to a displacement field of Mindlin can be written as follows:

$$[K]^{Mindlin} = [P]^t \cdot ([K]^{Kirchhoff} + [\Delta K]) \cdot [P] \quad (11)$$

$$[K]^M = [P]^t \cdot \left(\begin{bmatrix} K_m & K_{mb} \\ K_{bm} & K_b \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \Delta K_{mb} \\ \Delta K_{bm} & \Delta K_b + K_s \end{bmatrix} \right) \cdot [P] \quad (12)$$

$$[P] = \begin{bmatrix} \text{Ident. matrix} & 0 \\ 0 & P_{u_3, \text{corrected}} \end{bmatrix} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{correction linear operator} \\ \text{of transversal displacement interpolation functions.} \end{array}$$

The HRPM stiffness (without the shear transverse effects) matrix is represented by the Kirchhoff stiffness matrix corresponding to the Classical Plate Theory.

This conception of the stiffness matrix presents two advantages:

the first is to avoid the shear locking phenomenon when the ratio depth-to-thickness increases, as it can be seen on the following relations:

$$\lim_{\frac{a}{h} \rightarrow \infty} [K]^M \rightarrow [K]^K \quad \text{because } [P] \rightarrow [\text{Ident. matrix}] \text{ and } [\Delta K] \rightarrow [0] \quad (13)$$

the second is not to add extra degrees of freedom to the final element (HRPM-S) compared with the HRPM element.

Numerical results

The HRPM-S finite element developed in this paper was employed in bending problems of highly anisotropic multilayered composite rectangular plates. The numerical results are compared to the penalty plate-bending element of REDDY [5]. This finite element is a eight-node quadrilateral element. The uniform meshes are different for the two finite elements in order to have the almost same number of degrees-of-freedom:

325 for the REDDY finite element (4x4 mesh)

336 for the HRPM-S finite element (6x6 mesh)

The boundary conditions are simply-supported and two types of orthotropic materials were used. The material properties are:

$$\text{Material I: } E_1/E_2 = 25, \quad G_{12}/E_2 = 0.5, \quad G_{23}/E_2 = 0.2, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.25$$

$$\text{Material II: } E_1/E_2 = 40, \quad G_{12}/E_2 = 0.6, \quad G_{23}/E_2 = 0.5, \quad \nu_{12} = 0.25$$

$$\text{with } G_{12} = G_{13} \text{ and } \nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$$

The shear correction coefficients have the value of 5/6 [7].

The first analysis consists of the study of the bending deflection versus side-to-thickness ratio in comparison with the Reddy finite element solution for two angle-ply ($45^\circ / -45^\circ$) square plates under sinusoidal loading

$$p(x_1, x_2) = p_0 \cdot \cos \frac{\pi x_1}{a} \cdot \cos \frac{\pi x_2}{b}$$

Figure 3 shows plots of the nondimensionalized bending deflections for the material I:

$$\bar{w} = w E_2 h^3 10^3 / P_0 a^4$$

figure (3)

Figure 4 shows plots of the nondimensionalized bending deflections for the material II:

figure (4)

The second analysis consists of the study of the non existence of the shear locking when the side-to-thickness ratio becomes important. bending deflection versus side-to-thickness ratio in comparison with the SYSTUS finite element solution [8] for two angle-ply (45° / -45°) square plates under uniform pressure loading. The value of the CPT solution is taken to be the converged solution obtained by using a finite element model [6].

figure (5)

CONCLUSIONS

A formulation including the shear deformation effects in the Hermitian Rectangular Plate-Membrane element [10] has been developed by the application of a specific linear operator to the stiffness matrix of the thin plate. These two types of elements are more specialized for the highly anisotropic laminated plates. The different results presented here and in [9] prove the good accuracy and the non existence of the shear locking phenomenon when the side-to-thickness ratio becomes important. This element provides an efficient tool for assessing the response of thick and thin multilayer laminated plates whatever the stacking sequence of the laminated plate.

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